

Formation Of Gender Equality In University Students

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Abstract: *This article discusses issues related to the formation of the experience of sociocultural activities of students based on the use of a gender approach.*

Keywords — gender, student, teacher, education, pedagogy, activity, society, culture.

INTRODUCTION.

In our time, when the boundaries between the roles of men and women are blurred, and the possibilities for the manifestation of personal qualities become more diverse, the importance of gender studies increases significantly. They cross various fields of knowledge and contribute to the development of methods for solving problems both in science and in various spheres of public life.

The use of a gender approach in education opens up prospects for truly achieving gender equality and improving the well-being of both sexes. However, the desire to improve the quality of training of specialists and attract women to various fields of work faces the problem of “gender blindness” in vocational education, which still persists in Uzbek educational institutions, despite significant progress in gender studies in recent decades.

The need to develop gender studies in pedagogy is emphasized by the fact that traditional ideas about gender roles still prevail in the field of education, which leads to inequality and discrimination of students based on their gender. Modern democratic society is aimed at maintaining equal rights for all its participants, including gender equality. It is in this context that the education system plays a key role, becoming one of the tools in achieving this goal.

With the establishment of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan took a course towards integration into the world community, relying on democratic transformations. A key element of these transformations has become human rights, including gender equality, which is seen as a necessary condition for the sustainable development of the economy, social and cultural spheres of society. In this context, an important aspect is the formation of a culture of gender equality, which covers all areas of social relations and includes the education and promotion of gender culture. The state policy of Uzbekistan is aimed at disseminating educational activities in this area, which is confirmed by Decree of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. US-29 7-IV “On approval of the Strategy for achieving equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” dated May 28, 2021.

Gender equality includes equal possession by women and men of socially significant benefits, opportunities, resources and rewards.

It is important to note that gender equality does not mean identity between men and women, but guarantees equal opportunities and prospects in life.

The gender approach in education involves the study of gender as a social characteristic and taking into account the influence of various factors of the educational process on the development of boys and girls, as well as the characteristics of male and female psychology, reflected in their behavior, reactions and teaching style.

A study of recent research and publications on the formation of gender culture among students has revealed a number of problems existing in this area. The importance of this problem lies in the different approaches of scientists to understanding the essence of gender culture.

The gender approach to education involves analyzing gender as a social characteristic, as well as taking into account the impact of various factors in the educational process on the development of boys and girls. This approach also includes the study of male and female psychology as reflected in behavior, reactions and teaching style.

For example, H.M. Tozhiboeva emphasizes the importance of developing a friendly attitude, mutual respect and trust in others in children and adolescents. These aspects are considered as an integral part of the cultural worldview and play a role in the formation of immunity against the negative influence of “mass culture” [2, p. 47].

However, in addition to this approach, other points of view on the formation of gender culture can be found in scientific research, which indicates the diversity of opinions and approaches in this area.

V. Shvetsova[3] considers gender culture as a system of knowledge about the biosocial characteristics of men and women, including norms and values that organize their joint activities on the basis of equality, solidarity and partnership.

While V. Krainik and M. Mikova [4] highlight the gender culture of society, divided into male and female, which include areas of culture where accepted norms are different for different genders. They also emphasize that the gender culture

of an individual must correspond to social norms, values and rules of behavior.

L. Gradusova [5] connects gender culture with gender-role values, behavior and gender roles that reflect the “natural state of affairs.”

Based on the discussed points of view and the significance of this problem in the context of democratic transformations, it can be argued that the formation of gender culture is important for modern educational practice and pedagogical theory.

The views of educational scientists indicate that gender culture is a complex system that has its own specifics for everyone gender, expressed through the concepts of “woman’s culture” and “man’s culture”. This culture includes the formation of ideas about life purpose and positive qualities inherent in each gender, and also takes into account physiological and psychological characteristics.

The set of social values formed in a certain society during its history should determine the behavior of each individual, observing norms regarding both men and women. The declaration of the idea of gender equality is undeniable, since it is based on a binary opposition (femininity - masculinity) associated with the fulfillment of social roles, and also justifies belonging to a certain biological sex and differences in norms and social requirements for students.

Based on the analysis of existing definitions of gender culture, we can distinguish three main approaches to understanding its essence: semi-differentiated, socio-gender (sex-role) and gender itself.

A semi-differentiated approach implies the existence of separate cultures for each gender, highlighting female and male spheres of activity and behavior.

The process of targeted pedagogical influence on a person with the aim of developing certain socially and professionally significant qualities (worldview, knowledge, skills, attention, value orientations, certain relationships, etc.) is implemented by a specially organized set of content, forms, methods and means, and in pedagogy is defined as formation, which is a purposeful process of personal development under the influence of external influences of upbringing, training, social environment, as well as the formation of a student as a subject and object of social relations.

Creating a gender educational environment involves:

- creating conditions for unlocking potential and developing professional motivation, helping to improve the quality of training and demand for students in the labor market, regardless of gender;

- conducting campaigns to inform and motivate girls and women to choose non-stereotypical STEM careers (science, technology, engineering, mathematics);

The listed measures contribute to the development of gender equality in educational institutions:

1. Providing complete information about the possibilities of professional self-determination without taking into account stereotypes about female and male professions, allows subjects of the educational process to realize a wide range of choices in accordance with their abilities and interests.

2. Supporting women's leadership in educational institutions contributes to the development of equal opportunities for women and men in educational and management activities.

3. The spatial and subject design of higher educational institutions, including library collections and information resources enriched with materials on gender content, creates a supportive environment for awareness and acceptance of gender diversity.

4. Educational and methodological developments for curators and teachers of higher educational institutions contribute to the introduction of gender-sensitive approaches to the educational process and interaction with students.

5. Gender-sensitive visual design of the spatial environment (stands, posters, notice boards, etc.) expresses support for the principles of gender equality and contributes to the formation of an inclusive educational environment.

The study revealed and characterized the pedagogical conditions for the formation of students’ gender culture:

- Increasing the gender competence of teachers, especially curators of student groups, through the organization of methodological work. This includes training teachers in modern gender theories and methods, as well as their active use in the educational process and extracurricular activities.

- Creation of a gender-sensitive environment in a higher education institution based on the principles of gender equality. This means providing an educational environment that respects differences between the sexes and welcomes their equal participation and development.

- Involving students in extracurricular activities aimed at developing a gender culture, with an emphasis on mastering modern scientific gender knowledge as the basis for a value-based attitude to professional training. This may include workshops, discussions, projects and other activities aimed at creating awareness and understanding of gender issues and roles in society.

- These pedagogical conditions contribute to the effective formation of gender culture among students, which is important for their professional and personal development in modern society.

This analysis highlights the main components of the model of gender-oriented educational process:

1. Target component: The main objective of this component is to increase the level of gender orientation in the educational process. This is achieved by directing all methods, forms, means and conditions of the educational process to enrich it with gender content.

2. Operational component: Includes pedagogical conditions and technologies for organizing a gender-oriented educational process at the university. This includes teaching methods, organizing training activities and introducing specialized programs and courses.

3. Content component: Here we consider the content of pedagogical activities to fill the most significant components of the educational process with gender content. This may include studying gender topics, analyzing the gender aspects of educational materials, and developing gender-specific courses.

4. Criteria component: Here the criteria and indicators of the level of gender orientation of the educational process are determined. This may include assessing students' knowledge and understanding of gender issues, as well as assessing the effectiveness of implementing gender-sensitive teaching methods.

5. Effective component: It evaluates the achieved level of gender orientation of the educational process and its impact on students. This can be expressed through changes in students' worldviews, behavior and understanding of gender issues.

The set of pedagogical conditions necessary for the effective creation of a gender-oriented educational process is as follows:

- providing pedagogical support to teachers of a technical university in the field of familiarization with gender issues and terminology in the process of improving their teaching qualifications, familiarizing them with modern current problems in this area and increasing their motivation to consider gender issues in the classroom;

- development and implementation in the process of classes with students of a specialized course (optional) on gender knowledge and its corresponding educational and methodological support (program development

special course, its content, teaching aid on basic issues of tender education);

- creating a gender-friendly atmosphere of interaction, cooperation and partnership between subjects of the educational process, facilitating the implementation of training and education at a dialogic level.

Research on the formation of gender culture among students of higher educational institutions has a close connection with their involvement and participation in extracurricular activities aimed at developing gender culture and mastering modern scientific gender knowledge. Expanding forms of extracurricular activities helps create pedagogical conditions for the multifaceted development and self-realization of students, as well as for testing professional knowledge and skills. This also contributes to the development of interdisciplinary connections and the formation of general competencies of future teachers.

Extracurricular activities may include various activities such as seminars, trainings, discussions, conferences and project work on gender issues and their significance in

education and society. Students' participation in such events helps them understand the gender aspects of their professional activities, develop critical thinking and gender literacy, and also contributes to the formation of a tolerant and inclusive public opinion.

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